

How do Gender and Investment Income Affect Credit Management Among Small Business Persons? Evidence from Rural Erstwhile Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

Small businesses in rural India, providing off-farm employment, are primarily driven by credit. The present study surveyed 124 male and female rural businesspersons in four districts of AP and Telangana states, was conducted with two objectives-one, to understand the gender differences in small business investments; and two, to explore the differences in loan management and repayment between above-average and below-average investors. Chi-square tests for comparison of proportions and t-tests for comparing means reveal businesswomen less credit constrained than businessmen, arguably because of their SHG membership. Furthermore, controlling for business investment reveals that below average investors sell their products closer home and take longer for selling, than above-average investors, making their businesses less efficient. The lack of significant difference in the turnover and profit of below-average investors and above-average investors, throws light on the futility of scaling up. Finally, the paper finds critical differences in credit management strategies between genders as also between high and low investors.

Keywords: Small businesses, gender, credit, below average investment

Introduction

Micro-finance industry recognizes the potential for micro-credit to enhance the rural incomes and promotes small businesses. Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) and policy makers alike have responded through the design of innovative credit interventions, including promoting small businesses through credit and training. Grameen Bank in Bangladesh (Godquin, 2004; Zaman, 2004)), Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA), Mysore Resettlement and Development Agency (MYRADA), BASIX and National Bank of Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) in India (Fisher and Sriram, 2009), Palli Karma Sahayak foundation (PKSF) in Bangladesh are engaged in credit plus with an intention of enhancing small businesses.

Literature, while admitting to the link between credit access and business growth (Hartarska et.al, 2008), focused on credit constraint of women-owned businesses (Halkias et.al, 2011; Nwachuku et.al,

2008; Hussain et.al, 2008). Furthermore, small and medium enterprises in Ghana, observe Pecking Order Theory (PoH), preferring higher order credit, yet borrowing from lower-order finance (Osei-Assibey, 2011). While all the above examine the structural aspects of credit constraint, none of them compared the differences in credit terms between male and female businesspersons and the differences in their businesses. Hartarska (2008) compares the credit constrained and credit unconstrained small businesses in Bosnia and finds how credit constraint hinders newer entrepreneurs.

This study takes off from the literature and investigates two research objectives, namely, the gender differences in managing small businesses, and the income differences in managing small businesses, through 124 interviews of men and women, in four districts of Srikakulam, Nalgonda, Adilabad and Chittoor. The present study incorporates borrowing and repayment variables, capturing even prepayment behaviour in the investigation.

The low farm returns in the sampled districts, which averaged at Rs. 10,083 per acre, per annum, explain why small businesses are critical for off-farm income. A majority of the businesses in erstwhile AP were either handed down by the families, or dealt in low-skill retailing.

Furthermore, the meltdown of MFIs at the time of this study (2014), the primary sources of micro-credit were the state-supported women's Self-Help Groups (SHGs). This meant that SHG membership was important for credit access. This study shows how women managed businesses borrow and invest significantly more in small businesses than men, and points to a link between credit-group membership and business investment. Furthermore, controlling for business investment shows that below average investors invest significantly less than above average investors, but pay higher monthly instalments than the above-average investors. The below average investors operate closer home and take longer to sell their produce, highlighting the constraints in accessing markets for their products.

Literature Review

Credit Access and Small Businesses

Hartarska and Nadolnyak (2008), observe the link between micro-credit access and the sustenance of small enterprises in Bosnia and Herzegovina where they measure credit access by the number of MFIs operating in the given province. The MFIs in credit constrained provinces depend upon own funds for running their enterprises and are owned by experienced and skilled entrepreneurs, as against those in credit flush provinces, where the owners invest less of own funds and depend more on credit. Relative inexperience and lack of skill do not hamper investments in enterprises in credit flush provinces, leading to the upward mobility of the entrepreneurs (Hartarska and Nadolnyak, 2008). The lack of contribution of SMEs to growth has also been attributed to their credit constraint, particularly in reference to formal financial institutions (Beck and Demirguck-Kunt, 2006). The reasons for credit constraint of small businesses are many, information asymmetry and the inadequacy of the formal credit being the most important.

Information Asymmetry and Credit for Small Businesses

Micro-investments are marked by information opacity- the MFIs do not know the risks in borrowers' investments, prompting them to co-opt with moneylenders or loan officers who signal the MFIs about borrowers' creditworthiness. The superior informational advantage of the moneylender implies that the moneylender would lend only to low-risk borrowers, thereby signaling their creditworthiness to the MFIs (Jain and Mansuri, 2002). Information opacity is also blamed for small businesses' inability to attract external financing, who rely more on own finances, Berger and Udell (2002) note. Even though small businesses seek funds from formal banks and are

credit constrained on account of information opacity, relationship lending, a less formal lending technology, where the loan officer with a knowledge of the firm in question, can recommend loans to the same. Relationship lending relies heavily on the local knowledge of loan officers and if practiced, can help small businesses overcome their credit constraint (Berger and Udell, 2002).

On the flip side relationship lending can cause agency problems between the banks and the loan officers, and cannot be effectively practiced by large banks with multi-layered structure (Berger and Udell, 2002). In a study on the collateralization of Bolivian SMEs, Berger and Udell (2008) observe how relationship length between banks and SME borrowers reduces the information asymmetry, obliterating the need for a collateral. Relationship lending, based on inside information, not available in the public domain, and obtained through contacts, also reduces the risk of default where trust forms of cornerstone of a lending contract (Seal, 1990).

Tan, Yang and Veliyath (2009) investigate the origin and sustenance of Guanxi, a network of business and personal relationships in China. They observe how the SMEs in China benefit out of Guanxi, which emerged with the weakening of the formal institutions during the country's political transition. Furthermore, there are no gender differences in accessing finance through Guanxi, even though women businesspersons depended more on own finance than their male counterparts (Hussain et al., 2008).

Information asymmetry and the fear of ex post moral hazard leads to the credit constraint of small and medium firms in England, where a survey and a probit analysis of 16,101 firms reveals that the credit constraint of SMEs could be obliterated through collateralization. Growth firms face credit constraint more acutely than non-growth firms, prompting wealthier businesspersons not to apply for credit (Binks and Ennew, 2016; Atieno, 2001). Even though informal credit sources are convenient suppliers to small businesses on account of their flexibility, they do not help much for scaling up, and instead confining themselves to specific activities in the lower level of credit requirement, creating a credit gap (Atieno, 2001).

Credit Choices Available to the Rural Businesses

The lack of information and security compelled the businesspersons in Kenya to obtain credit only from formal lenders, failing which, they were left with few credit choices, leading to credit rationing. Limited credit access in Kenya is due to supply-side constraint and not a demand- side constraint- lenders offering different credit packages to different borrowers often fail to meet the variegated credit needs of the borrowers (Atieno, 2001). There existed a Pecking Order Theory (PoH) in Thai credit-markets where the small businesses prefer accessing higher-order formal credit, but end up borrowing from lower-order finance, for want of wealth, education and a bank account (Osei-Assibey et.al, 2012).

Unequal Credit Constraint

Inequality in credit constraint implied women, minorities and other socially disadvantaged groups were more constrained than the rest. In the US, black-owned businesses are three times more

likely to be denied a loan than their white-owned counterparts, and the factors hampering businesses affect black more than those of whites (Blanchflower and Levine, 1998). In India, where caste-based discrimination is prevalent in district cooperative banks, the lower caste borrowers belonging to the scheduled castes and tribes are credit more constrained than the upper caste borrowers (Mitra Kumar, 2013).

Even where there is a credit access, cost-rationing is practiced towards specific groups like blacks (Blanchflower and Levine, 1998); women (Coleman, 2000) and the poor (Barham et.al,

1996; Stiglitz and Weiss, 1981). Women not only pay a higher interest for credit, but their loans are also collateralized more often in the USA, on account of their credit constraint in the formal credit market (Coleman, 2000). Lenders offer differing lending contracts to different classes of borrowers, where the poor are either cost-rationed or size-rationed (Barham et.al, 1996; Stiglitz and Weiss, 1981). Similarly, women owner-managers of farms in Punjab in India are denied credit by formal banks and are forced to borrow from moneylenders at a higher cost, despite offering a collateral (Sandhu, 2012); while female businesspersons, who are not otherwise credit constrained in Canada, face a systematic discrimination by lending officers (Fabowale, Orser and Riding, 2016).

Caribbean women pride holding a paid job, even while spending time on unpaid domestic work (Messiah, 1986) continues to be women's source of pride. Warwire and Nafukho (2010) observe that in Kenya women's sexual roles leave them with little time for managing their Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs). Madiche and NKambene (2010) observe how internal, socio-cultural factors and a lack of supportive regulatory framework, hinder small businesses in Nigeria. Halkias et.al, (2012) find gender discrimination in credit access in industrialized provinces of Nigeria, used to the western way of doing business, hinting at inherent differences between western and non-western countries in their gender perception. Hussain et.al, (2010) likewise found no gender differences in accessing finance from Guanxi among Chinese businesspersons, unlike those in the UK where women had a greater chance of getting rejected for bank loans. Sanderberg (2003), nevertheless, found no gender differences in small businesses' financials and management in Switzerland. Do female businesspersons face credit constraint more than men in India? Do they borrow and repay differently than men? What are the differences in the credit choices available to men and women? I investigate through the second first objective.

RO1: To investigate the gender differences in accessing credit amongst small businesspersons
Credit management amidst inequality:

Credit access is unequal with respect to formal credit partly on account of risk aversion of the poorer farmers who refuse to pledge collateral, and instead borrow from moneylenders, often at a premium (Chiu, Khantachavana and Turvey, 2014).

The credit markets have shown wealth bias, with the poorer of the borrowers cost rationed and size-rationed (Barham et.al, 1996; Stiglitz and Weiss, 1981). As a strong response to the market bias the poor seek credit group membership or tap informal networks for credit access (Wydick et.al, 2006; Turvey and Kong, 2010). Yet both Barham et.al, (1996) who based their study in Ivory Coast; and Yuan and Xu (2015) who base their study in China, point out that the poorest of the poor get excluded from credit cooperatives, and from informal networks. How do the poorest businesspersons invest in India? What are their credit terms? How do they differ from above-average investors in marketing their produce? I address these questions through the next research objectives.

RO2: How do the poorest of the investors manage their credit differently from the above average investors?

Methodology

We conducted interviews of 124 male and female small businesspersons in four districts of erstwhile AP. The districts were sampled based on credit access through SHGs, where we selected chose the top (Chittoor), bottom (Nalgonda) and two moderate recipient districts (Srikakulam and Adilabad) of credit through SHGs. This was the first stage of cluster sampling. In stage two, we randomly select a village from each of these districts, where we interviewed 31 businessmen and women per village. The businesspersons include retailers, traditional craft-persons like blacksmiths, tailors and off-farm dealers.

Variables of Study**Table 1 Variables for Demographic Information of Borrowers**

S. No	Variable	Agricultural Variables
1.	Village name	No. of acres of farm owned
2.	District name	Whether the crop is annual or biannual
3.	Age	Income from crop 1 Rs.
4.	Gender	Income from crop 2 Rs.
5.	Marital status	Govt./MFI providing the following facilities
6.	Caste	Grain storage
7.	Religion	Milk chilling
8.	Education	Better poultry feed
9.	Family size	Fertilizers
10.	Income from all sources per month in Rs.	Seeds
11.	Number of earning members in the family	Other facilities
12.	Number of banks in the village	
13.	Distance to the nearest bank in Km.	
14.	No. of SHGs in the village	
15.	Whether the borrower has a bank account	
16.	Whether the borrower is a chit fund member	
17.	Whether the borrower is the member of an SHG	

Table 2 Variables for Loan Information and Credit Preference

S. No	Variables for loans	Variables for credit preference
1.	No. of years of borrowing	Rank for Bank credit from 1 to 6
2.	No. of loans taken so far	Rank of SHG-bank 1 loan from 1 to 6
3.	Amount outstanding for loan 1 and 2 in Rs.	Rank of SHG-own funds from 1 to 6
4.	Source of loan 1 and 2	Rank of moneylenders' loan from 1 to 6
5.	Purpose of loan 1 and 2	Rank of loan from friends and relatives from 1 to 6
6.	Use of loan 1 and 2	Rank of loan from farmers /traders from 1 to 6
7.	Interest per month on loan 1 and 2	
8.	Time-lag in months, between application and approval of loan 1 & 2	
9.	Due date in months for loans 1 and 2	
10.	Whether borrower borrows during time-lag	
11.	Whether borrower postpones during time-lag	

Table 3 Variables for Loan Management

S. No	Variable for installment finance choices	Incentives for loan recovery (Hypothetical)	Repayment reasons (Real)	Type
1.	Returns from agri/ small businesses	Interest waiver	Agri/Biz profits	Binary
2.	Savings	Principal waiver	Regular wages	Binary
3.	Salaries/ wages	Promise of bigger loan	Fear of loss of future loan	Binary
4.	Hand-loans from friends & relatives	Promise of another loan	Good economy	Binary
5.	Through moneylenders' loan	Promise of a cheaper loan	Loan used for the purpose it was meant for	Binary
6.	By cutting on food and clothing	Other incentive	Low interest	Binary
7.	Through other methods		Promise of a future loan	Binary
			Promise of a bigger loan	Binary
			Repay even otherwise	Binary

Table 4 Variables capturing default, Prepayment and collateral information

S. No	Variable for default & Prepayment	Nature	Variable for collateralization	Nature
1.	Whether the borrower defaulted or not	Binary	Whether the borrower offered a collateral or not	Binary
2.	Amount defaulted in Rs.	Continuous	Value of the collateral	Continuous
3.	Duration of default	Categorical	Amount borrowed against collateral	Continuous
4.	Lender whom he defaulted with	Categorical	Lender to whom collateral was offered	Categorical
5.	Reasons for default	Qualitative	Whether guarantee is a collateral substitute	Binary
6.	Consequences of default	Qualitative	Int. on moneylenders' loan/month	Continuous
7.	Whether the borrower prepaid or not	Binary		
8.	Reasons for prepayment	Qualitative		

Table 5 Variables Capturing the Nature of Small Businesses

S. No	Variable for nature of small businesses	Variable type		Variable type
1.	Whether the borrower invested in small business the year before	Binary	Market distance in Km	Categorical
2.	Which business?	Qualitative	Whether the borrower received training for business mgmt.?	Binary

3.	Amount invested in business	Continuous	Whether the MFI/ NGO provide any training on • Business mgmt.? • Marketing products? • Book-keeping? • Production? • Literacy/ health issues • Any other type?	Binary
4.	Amount of loan in investment	Continuous		
5.	Monthly installment for this loan	Continuous		
6.	Turnover per month/ week	Continuous		
7.	Profit per month	Continuous		
8.	How quickly the product gets sold?	Categorical		

Descriptives

Table 6: Demographics and borrowing values for small businesspersons

Variable	Avg. Value	Largest loan sourced from	Percentage
Age	41.31	Nationalized banks	48.38
Income per month Rs.	5342	RRBs	4
% with bank account	90.33	SHG-Bank loan	5.6
% with chit-fund / cooperative membership	12.09	Moneylenders	30.64
Average amount invested in business	53,277	Friends & relatives	4.8
Average annual income from two crops Rs.	9,642	Farmer/ trader	4.8
Total loan Rs.	98,181	MFI/JLG/ Chit/Gold	1.6
% of women	16.12	% men in credit groups	9.6
% women in SHGs, JLGs or both	90		

Tables 1 to 5 above capture the variables used in the study. These include variables related to the borrowing behaviour; credit management; demographics and the nature of the business of the small businesspersons interviewed. Table 6 shows that 16% of the businesspersons interviewed are women and the rest are men. The average land-holding size of the small businesspersons is 0.97 acre, which reflects the marginality of farming. The average annual income from farms is Rs.9, 672, which amounts to a mere Rs.806 per month, while the average monthly income from all sources is Rs.5, 342, pointing to the role of off-farm activities and businesses in providing additional income to the household.

Results

We investigate the first research objective, namely, gender differences in accessing credit amongst small businesspersons. We run t-test and chi-square tests, as the case maybe, after controlling for gender for identifying differences in borrowing and management of small businesses (Table 10).

Table 10 Results of the independent sample t-test after controlling for gender

Variable	Mean difference between men and women	Standard error	t-value	Significance
Amt. invested in biz Rs.	-24,715	14828	-1.667 (122)	0.001
Monthly income Rs.	-1255.57	873.88	-1.437 (122)	0.018

Crop 1 income Rs.	-3930	2458.48	-1.599(122)	0.003
Crop 2 income Rs.	-5963	5562.75	-1.072(122)	0.022
Time-lag 1 : months	-0.5661	0.45687	-1.239(122)	0.074
Time-lag 2 : months	-0.766	0.395	-1.937 (105)	0.011
Total loans Rs.	-37786.152	21509.686	-1.757 (122)	0.001
Interest on loan 2 per month	0.732	0.352	2.073(103)	0.041
Loan 2 due date months	-6.658	3.013	-2.2 (100)	0.053
Loan amount in investment Rs.	-19,481.73	10,986	-1.77(122)	0.057
how quickly product is sold	1.508	1.149	1.31(122)	0.000

The t-test run on various demographic variables after controlling for gender reveals that, business- women’s relative wealth is significantly more than that of businessmen, as measured by monthly income from all sources, and income from the two crops. Women are significantly more indebted than men, and hence, the due date is significantly longer for women than it is for men. Women wait significantly longer for loan sanction, as measured by the time-lag between the application and approval of loan. Women borrow their second loan at lower interest rates than men.

The t-test for business related variables after controlling for gender shows that, Women invest significantly more in small businesses, while the products sold by men have a longer shelf- life than those sold by women, pointing to the perishability of women’s products.

Chi-square tests reveal gender differences in borrowing and repayment strategy of small business-persons (Table 11).

Table 11 Comparison between Genders for Borrowing and Repayment Strategies

Variable	Chi- square value	Chi- square significance	Continuity correction	p-value for continuity correction	Result
Prepayment	0.083	0.773	0.000	1	No difference between genders in prepayment
Source of loan 2	45.802	0.000	-	-	Men borrow from moneylenders & nationalized banks; women borrow from SHGs, moneylenders and nationalized banks in that order
Purpose of loan 1	23.177	0.01	-	-	More women borrow loan 1 for agriculture and more men, for consumption purposes.
Trade	16.55	0.011	-	-	More women than men are involved in off-farm activities
Family size	10.58	0.161	-	-	No difference
No. of earning members in family	7.782	0.1	-	-	Women have more earning members in family
Caste	14.75	0.002	-	-	More women are OCs than men. More men are BCs than women
Education	6.78	0.148	-	-	No difference
Holding bank account	0.824	0.662	-	-	No difference
Being a chit or a cooperative member	3.735	0.154	-	-	No difference
Lenders’ flexibility	1.51	0.219	-	-	No difference
Repayment priority	2.635	0.105	-	-	No difference

Installment finance choices					
• Friends /relatives	0.361	0.548	-	-	No difference Men borrow more from moneylender Women save more No difference No difference No difference No difference
• Moneylenders	4.857	0.028	-	-	
• Savings	6.53	0.011	-	-	
• Investment	0.389	0.533	-	-	
• income	0.013	0.91	-	-	
• Cut on food/ clothes	0.004	0.948	-	-	
• Salary/wages	0.254	0.615	-	-	
• Others					
Defaulted before? Y/N	2.513	0.113	-	-	No difference
Lender whom you defaulted with	46.171	0.000	-	-	Men fail to pay moneylenders and banks more; Women fail to pay banks and SHGs
Credit preference:					
• Banks	18.54	0.002	-	-	No difference
• SHG-Bank	26.63	0.00	-	-	Men lower, women higher preference
• SHG-own funds	17.76	0.003	-	-	Men lower, women higher preference
• MFI-JLG loans	3.257	0.66	-	-	Men lower, women higher preference
• Moneylender loans	16.53	0.005	-	-	No difference
• Friends/ relatives					Men prefer more than women
Given collateral before?	4.245	0.12	-	-	No difference
Collateral, which lender?	1.051	0.902	-	-	No difference
Guarantee a collateral substitute?	4.057	0.044	-	-	Women find guarantors more
Repayment reason:					
• Agri/ biz profits			0.114	2.49	More men and fewer women use profits
• Regular wages			-	-	No difference
• Repay otherwise also	3.557	0.059	-	-	No difference
• Loss of future loans	0.812	0.367	-	-	No difference
• Good economy	0.117	0.732	-	-	No difference
• Loan used for the purpose it was borrowed for	0.209	0.647	-	-	No difference
• Low interest	8.165	0.004	-	-	More men disagree; more women agree
• Get another/ bigger loan	0.081	0.776	-	-	No difference
	1.321	0.25	-	-	No difference

Next, I investigate the second research objective, namely, studying the impact of income inequality and investment inequality on credit management of small businesspersons. Descriptives reveal that the average amount invested in businesses in AP and Telangana is Rs.53, 277. I control for the average and divide the data into above and below average investors. t-tests and chi-square tests reveal the differences in the demographics, borrowing, credit preference and repayment strategies of the below-average and above-average investors (Tables 12 and 13).

Table 12 Results of the Independent Sample t-test after Controlling for Investment Amount

Variable	Mean difference between below and above average investors	Standard error	t-value	Significance	Result
No. of banks in the village	-0.2804	0.2446	-1.146	0.057	More banks in villages with above- average investors
Monthly income	-1588.4	708.58	-2.242	0.004	More income for above-average investors
Crop income 2	12489.87	4460.1	-2.8	0.000	More crop income among below average investors
Time-lag 2	-1.4	0.303	-4.66	0.000	Greater time- lag for loan 2 between application and approval of loan among above average investors
Time-lag1	-1.82	0.338	-5.3	0.000	Greater time- lag for loan 1 between application and approval of loan among above average investors
Moneylenders' interest per month	0.15	0.3	0.501	0.043	Higher moneylender interest rates for below average investors
Monthly installment for biz loan Rs.	-1147.59	924.733	-1.011	0.738	No difference
Turnover per month Rs.	-6708.33	4352.72	-1.54	0.358	No difference
Profit per month Rs.	1778.76	1412.36	-1.25	0.41	No difference
How quickly product gets sold	0.8388	0.9122	-0.92	0.518	No difference
Market distance Km	-0.1286	1.48	-0.087	0.804	No difference

Below average investors expectedly are relatively poor, as indicated by a lower monthly income and live in a credit scarce environment, as revealed by the number of banks in the village; and pay a higher interest on moneylenders' loans, perhaps a consequence of credit scarcity (Table 12). Nevertheless, they get a faster loan sanction, as indicated by the lower time-lag between application and approval of the two loans, due to their smaller loan sizes. Even though, the monthly installment for business loan and turnover per month are lower for the below-average investors, the monthly profit is higher, though not significantly so. Furthermore, the below average investors take longer to sell their products, and operate closer home than the above average investors.

Chi-square tests for independence reveal the differences in borrowing and repayment, between the above and below average investors (Table 13).

Table 13 Comparison between below average and above average investors in borrowing and repayment behaviour

Variable	Chi-square value	Chi- square significance	Continuity correction	p- value for continuity correction	Result
Prepayment	4.396	0.036	2.878	0.09	Below average investors prepay less
Source of loan 1	9.463	0.221	-	-	No difference
Source of loan 2	7.708	0.463	-	-	No difference
Purpose of loan 1	2.967	0.982	-	-	No difference
Purpose of loan 2	8.381	0.496	-	-	No difference
Gender	0.001	0.979	-	-	No difference
Caste	3.274	0.351	-	-	No difference
Trade	9.025	0.172	-	-	No difference
Education	1.793	0.774	-	-	No difference
Holding bank account	1.077	0.584	-	-	No difference
Being a chit or a cooperative member	8.673	0.013	-	-	Below average investors have chit/cooperative membership more
Lenders' flexibility for loan 1	0.688	0.407	-	-	No difference
Repayment priority 1	8.34	0.004	7.232	0.007	Fewer below average investors have loan 1 as 1st repayment priority
Installment finance choices	2.414	0.12	1.825	0.177	No difference
• Friends/relatives	0.416	0.519	0.195	0.659	No difference
• Moneylenders	3.44	0.064	2.64	0.104	More below average investors repay through savings
• Savings	2.719	0.099	2.049	0.152	No difference
• Investment income	3.43	0.064	2.641	0.104	Below average investors cut consumption more
• Cut on food/clothes	0.969	0.325	0.610	0.435	No difference
• Salary/wages	0.288	0.591	0.018	0.893	No difference
• Others					
Defaulted before? Y/N	2.052	0.152	1.513	0.219	No difference
Credit preference:	5.764	0.217	-	-	No difference
• Banks	10.39	0.065	-	-	Below average investors give top preference
• SHG-Bank	1.022	0.051	-	-	Below average investors give bottom preference
• SHG-own funds	5.222	0.389	-	-	
• MFI-JLGloans	6.491	0.261	-	-	
• Money lender loans	10.72	0.057	-	-	No difference
• Friends/relatives					Below average investors give to pranks No difference
Given collateral before?	13.16	0.001			Above average investors give collateral more

Collateral, which lender?	1.967	0.742			No difference
Guarantee a collateral substitute?	0.242	0.622	0.000	1.000	No difference
Repayment reason:					
• Agri/ biz profits					
• Regular wages					
• Repay otherwise also	4.001	0.045	3.054	0.081	Below average investors repay less through agri returns
• Loss of future loans	0.918	0.338	0.573	0.449	No difference No difference
• Good economy	1.335	0.248	0.269	0.604	Below average investors fear loss of future loans more
• Loan used for the purpose it was borrowed for	4.27	0.023	3.22	0.073	Below average investors promise to repay if the economy is good, much more than above average investors
• Low interest	9.942	0.002	8.301	0.004	No difference
• Get another/ bigger loan	2.095	0.148	1.483	0.223	No difference No difference
	0.775	0.379	0.452	0.501	
	0.094	0.759	0.008	0.927	

Conclusions

Women in Small Businesses

The sampled small businesswomen are relatively wealthier than small businessmen and invested larger sums in business. Furthermore, businesswomen belong to upper castes and more men, to backward castes. Businesswomen borrow significantly larger loans and pay a significantly lower interest rate than the businessmen. Considering that 90% of women borrowers are members of either SHGs or JLGs, and just over 9% of small businessmen are chit-fund members, women access credit easier than men. Consequently, women invest more in small businesses, linking microcredit to small business investment.

While there is no gender difference in default and prepayment behaviour, there are differences in who the businesspersons default on. While men default more on moneylenders and banks in that order, women default on SHGs and banks. This result is backed by businesswomen's low preference for moneylenders' loans for financing installments, as compared to businessmen,

who appear to be borrowing from moneylenders for installment finance, and falling into debt traps. Small businesses in Thailand preferred formal credit, even while they are compelled to borrow from informal sources due to the former's wealth bias (Osei-Assibi, 2011), a finding backed by our results in India.

While there are no gender differences in offering collateral, businesswomen more than businessmen find guarantors as a collateral substitute, pointing to women's propensity to find nurturing relationships. Berger and Udell (2008) observe how small businesses' credit access depended upon relationship lending, while Jain and Mansuri (2002) proved how MFIs co-opted with moneylenders to reduce information asymmetry. Moneylenders and friends and relatives financing small businesses, underscore these findings.

Below average businesses

The smaller investors are less wealthy. Yet, there is no difference in turnover, profit, monthly installment size and other business-related variables between above and below average investors, pointing to the futility of scaling up. The intrinsic nature of small businesses, which propels profits, needs further investigation. Nevertheless, below average investors prepay less, signaling lower cash-flows. Prepayment is more of a portfolio management decision, signaling adequate cash-

flows, as it did, in Bausperkaan housing loans in Germany (Ceilback, 2008). The below average investors have the top most loan as the second in repayment priority, which the repay by cutting on consumption or through savings, and not from agricultural returns. This is unlike the above-average investors. The income inadequacy and potential distress of these businesspersons are evident, when compared to the above-average counterparts. The adverse financial circumstances compel them to cut consumption or to rely on savings for instalment financing. Income inadequacy could further cause an external locus of control, where smaller investors believing they could repay if the economy were good. Their repayment is further driven by a fear of loss of future loans, much more than the above average businesspersons, pointing to the credit market's potential bias against the poorest borrowers (Berham et al., 1996).

The below average businesspersons prefer lower order finance including SHG-bank credit and moneylenders, which, despite their flexibility, are unhelpful in scaling up, much like in Kenya (Antieno, 2001).

Discussion

This study examines the repayment strategies of small business-persons; an aspect not been investigated in detail in literature. The study fails to link investment amount, profits and even installment sizes, pointing to the low-profitability of small businesses in southern India. The complete absence of the state or the MFI in training the micro-entrepreneurs, as on 2014, severely curtails their ability to diversify, and the credit constraint prevents a scale-up.

The low farm returns in AP and Telangana imply the state needs to scale-up and promote off-farm activities, reinforcing an ecosystem for credit access and credit absorption. In the pre- MFI meltdown era, the credit plus ensued sufficient number small businesses were floated and sustained. The meltdown in contrast, adversely affected the sector. While the credit continues to be sourced from SHGs, there is a complete lack of training and hand-holding support to small businesses. Given the inadequacy of crop incomes, the investors need to diversify in unrelated and sometimes unknown domains. The diversification itself is not possible without the hand-holding support from the state and the NABARD. These agencies should step up their credit plus initiatives and fillip the small businesses, much like in Kenya (Atieno, 2001).

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